

Hyjazie and Forrest, 2023: Data Organization and Code

April 20, 2023

Set-Up

Load Packages

Main Manuscript

Data Organization: Year 1

1. Flower-Visitor Abundance

```
# Loading Excel file
Abundance_Osmia_Y1 <- read_excel("Osmia_Abundance_1.xlsx")

# Merging variable names (Orchard (the logistical orchard name according to orchard pairings) and Site ID)
Abundance_Osmia_1 <- Abundance_Osmia_Y1 %>% unite('Site', Orchard, `Site ID`, remove = FALSE)

# Verifying that Site = 24 and Orchard = 16
Abundance_Osmia_1_Site_Count <- n_distinct(Abundance_Osmia_1$Site)
Abundance_Osmia_1_Site_Count

Abundance_Osmia_1_Orchard_Count <- n_distinct(Abundance_Osmia_1`Orchard ID`)
Abundance_Osmia_1_Orchard_Count

# Summarizing *Osmia* counts per transect walk according to plot, Orchard ID (the proper orchard name), Round, and Site
Abundance_Osmia_1 <- Abundance_Osmia_1 %>% group_by(Plot, `Orchard ID`, Round, Site) %>%
  summarise_at(vars(Count), list(Count=sum))
```

1.1 *Osmia* spp. Abundance

1.2 All Flower Visitors All flower visitors during year 1.

```
# Loading Excel file
Abundance_Total_Y1 <- read_excel("Total_Abundance_1.xlsx")

# Merging variable names (Orchard and Site ID) to create unique identifiers for every site in new column
Abundance_Total_1 <- Abundance_Total_Y1 %>% unite('Site', Orchard, `Site ID`, remove = FALSE)

# Summarizing counts per transect walk according to plot, Orchard ID (the proper orchard name), Round, and Site
Abundance_Total_1 <- Abundance_Total_1 %>% group_by(Plot, `Orchard ID`, Round, Site) %>%
  summarise_at(vars(Count), list(Count=sum))
```

1.3 Small Flower Visitors Year 1; excludes honeybees and bumblebees.

```
# Loading Excel file
Abundance_Select_Y1 <- read_excel("Total_Abundance_1.xlsx")

# Merging variable names (Orchard and Site ID) to create unique identifiers for every site in new column
Abundance_Select_1 <- Abundance_Select_Y1 %>% unite('Site', Orchard, `Site ID`, remove = FALSE)

#Creating small insect subset
Abundance_Select_1 <- Abundance_Select_1 %>% filter(Taxa != "Apis", Taxa != "Bombus", Taxa != "Bombus Q

# Summarizing counts per transect walk according to plot, Orchard ID (the proper orchard name), Round, Site
Abundance_Select_1 <- Abundance_Select_1 %>% group_by(Plot, `Orchard ID`, Round, Site) %>%
  summarise_at(vars(Count), list(Count=sum))
```

2. Apple Yield and Quality

```
# Loading Excel File
Apple_1 <- read_excel("Apple_1.xlsx")

# Merging variable names (Orchard and Site ID) to create unique identifiers for every site in new column
Apple_1 <- Apple_1 %>% unite('Site', Orchard, `Site ID`, remove = FALSE)

# Re-labeling columns
Apple_1$Mean_Circum <- as.numeric(Apple_1$`Mean Non-Zero Circumference (cm)`)

# Creating columns for total fruit and bud numbers per tree (N + S branches)
Apple_1$Buds <- Apple_1$`N Bud #` + Apple_1$`S Bud #`
Apple_1$Pre_Fruit <- Apple_1$`N Pre-Thinning Fruit #` + Apple_1$`S Pre-Thinning Fruit #`
Apple_1$Post_Fruit <- Apple_1$`N Post-Thinning Fruit #` + Apple_1$`S Post-Thinning Fruit #`

# Replacing NA values for post-fruit apple with 0
Apple_1 <- Apple_1 %>%
  mutate(Post_Fruit=replace_na(Post_Fruit, 0))

# Calculating fruit set pre- and post-thinning
Apple_1$Fruit_Set_Pre <- Apple_1$Pre_Fruit/Apple_1$Buds
Apple_1$Fruit_Set_Post <- Apple_1$Post_Fruit/Apple_1$Buds

# Verifying that Site = 24 and Orchard = 16
Apple_1_Site_Count <- n_distinct(Apple_1$Site)
Apple_1_Site_Count

Apple_1_Orchard_Count <- n_distinct(Apple_1$`Orchard ID`)
Apple_1_Orchard_Count
```

Results: Year 1

1. Flower-Visitor Abundance

```
# Sum of counts by Taxa per Round
Total_Abundance_1_Sum <- Abundance_Total_Y1 %>%
  group_by(Taxa, Round) %>%
  dplyr::summarize_at(vars(Count), list(Count=sum))
Total_Abundance_1_Sum
```

```
## # A tibble: 57 x 3
## # Groups:   Taxa [23]
##   Taxa      Round      Count
##   <chr>   <chr>      <dbl>
## 1 Andrena Apple Bloom    304
## 2 Andrena Round 2       153
## 3 Andrena Round 3       626
## 4 Ant     Round 2         3
## 5 Apis    Apple Bloom   2123
## 6 Apis    Round 2       323
## 7 Apis    Round 3       573
## 8 Beetle  Apple Bloom    17
## 9 Beetle  Round 2        5
## 10 Beetle Round 3         2
## # i 47 more rows
```

```
#Means and SEs by plot (treatment) across sites and rounds
Abundance_Osmia_Means_1 <- Abundance_Osmia_1 %>%
  group_by(Plot) %>%
  dplyr::summarize_at(vars(Count), list(Mean_Count = mean, SE_Count = se))
Abundance_Osmia_Means_1
```

1.1 *Osmia* spp. Abundance

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 3
##   Plot      Mean_Count SE_Count
##   <chr>      <dbl>   <dbl>
## 1 Control      0.958   0.176
## 2 Treatment    1.5     0.295
```

```
# Overall Percent Difference between treatments for *Osmia* based on mean counts for each sampling round
Abundance_Osmia_Means_1 %>%
  summarise(percent_diff = ((Mean_Count[2] - Mean_Count[1])/mean(Mean_Count)))
```

```
##   percent_diff
## 1      0.440678
```

```
# *Osmia* summed across Rounds
Abundance_Osmia_Values_1 <- Abundance_Osmia_1 %>%
  group_by(Plot, Site) %>%
  dplyr::summarize_at(vars(Count), list(Total_Osmia_Count = sum))
Abundance_Osmia_Values_1
```

```
## # A tibble: 48 x 3
## # Groups:   Plot [2]
##   Plot   Site Total_Osmia_Count
##   <chr>  <chr>         <dbl>
## 1 Control CO_1             3
## 2 Control FO_3             5
## 3 Control HA_1             1
## 4 Control HA_2             2
## 5 Control HA_3             1
## 6 Control HC_1             1
## 7 Control KO_1             2
## 8 Control LC_1             4
## 9 Control MA_1             1
## 10 Control MA_2            6
## # i 38 more rows
```

```
#Means by plot (treatment) of abundance values summed across rounds
Abundance_Osmia_Totals_1 <- Abundance_Osmia_Values_1 %>%
  group_by(Plot) %>%
  dplyr::summarize_at(vars(Total_Osmia_Count), list(Mean_Total_Osmia = mean, SE_Count = se))
Abundance_Osmia_Totals_1
```

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 3
##   Plot      Mean_Total_Osmia SE_Count
##   <chr>          <dbl>     <dbl>
## 1 Control          2.88     0.508
## 2 Treatment         4.5     0.878
```

```
# Overall Percent Difference between treatments for *Osmia*, based on site totals:
Abundance_Osmia_Totals_1 %>%
  summarise(percent_diff = ((Mean_Total_Osmia[2]-Mean_Total_Osmia[1])/mean(Mean_Total_Osmia)))
```

```
##   percent_diff
## 1      0.440678
```

```
# Mean and SE of Percent Difference between Site pairs:
Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site <- pivot_wider(Abundance_Osmia_Values_1, names_from = Plot, values_from = Abundance_Osmia_Values_1)
Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Diff <- Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Treatment - Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Control
Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Mean_Abd <- (Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Treatment+Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Control)/2
Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Percent_Diff <- 100*Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Diff/Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Mean_Abd
```

```
## # A tibble: 24 x 6
##   Site Control Treatment Diff Mean_Abd Percent_Diff
##   <chr>  <dbl>     <dbl> <dbl>  <dbl>     <dbl>
## 1 CO_1      3         2     -1     2.5      -40
## 2 FO_3      5        10      5     7.5     66.7
## 3 HA_1      1         2      1     1.5     66.7
## 4 HA_2      2         3      1     2.5      40
## 5 HA_3      1         1      0      1         0
## 6 HC_1      1         0     -1     0.5    -200
## 7 KO_1      2        13     11     7.5    147.
```

```
## 8 LC_1      4      3    -1     3.5     -28.6
## 9 MA_1      1      4      3     2.5      120
## 10 MA_2     6      6      0      6         0
## # i 14 more rows
```

```
mean(Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Percent_Diff); sd(Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Percent
```

```
## [1] 32.93349
```

```
## [1] 20.48103
```

```
# Is there a difference between control and treatment plots for Osmia abundance, and does the treatment
```

```
#First look at data distribution:
```

```
hist(Abundance_Osmia_1$Count)
```

Histogram of Abundance_Osmia_1\$Count

1.1.1 Models

Abundance_Osmia_1\$Count

```
#Initial model (Poisson):
```

```
Osmia_Abund_GLMM_1 <- glmer(Count ~ Plot*Round + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
  family=poisson(link = "log"),
  data=Abundance_Osmia_1)
```

```
# Model diagnostics:
```

```
overdisp.glmer(Osmia_Abund_GLMM_1)
```

```
## Residual deviance: 246.107 on 136 degrees of freedom (ratio: 1.81)
```

```
testDispersion(Osmia_Abund_GLMM_1)
```

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 0.032

```
##  
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.  
## simulated  
##  
## data: simulationOutput  
## dispersion = 2.0773, p-value = 0.032  
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
simulationOutput <- simulateResiduals(fittedModel = Osmia_Abund_GLMM_1, plot = F)  
plot(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA residual


```
testZeroInflation(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA zero-inflation test via comparison to expected zeros with simulation under H_0 = fitted model

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p -value (two.sided) = 0.064

```
##
## DHARMA zero-inflation test via comparison to expected zeros with
## simulation under H0 = fitted model
##
## data: simulationOutput
## ratioObsSim = 1.2584, p-value = 0.064
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

#Some problems here, so try zero-inflated model fit instead.

#Zero-inflated Poisson using glmmTMB:

```
Osmia_Abund_ZI_1 <- glmmTMB(Count ~ Plot*Round + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
  ziformula = ~1 , family = "poisson",
  data=Abundance_Osmia_1)
```

#Diagnostics

```
testDispersion(Osmia_Abund_ZI_1)
```

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 0.584

```
##
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.
## simulated
##
## data: simulationOutput
## dispersion = 1.1479, p-value = 0.584
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
simulationOutput <- simulateResiduals(fittedModel = Osmia_Abund_ZI_1, plot = F)
plot(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA residual


```
#Results of selected model:
summary(Osmia_Abund_ZI_1)
```

```
## Family: poisson ( log )
## Formula:      Count ~ Plot * Round + (1 | 'Orchard ID'/Site)
## Zero inflation: ~1
## Data: Abundance_Osmia_1
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
##    451.9    478.6  -216.9   433.9     135
##
## Random effects:
##
## Conditional model:
## Groups      Name      Variance Std.Dev.
## Site:'Orchard ID' (Intercept) 0.29519  0.5433
## Orchard ID    (Intercept) 0.05407  0.2325
## Number of obs: 144, groups: Site:'Orchard ID', 26; Orchard ID, 16
##
## Conditional model:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)   -0.6608    0.4111  -1.607  0.10798
## PlotTreatment    1.1043    0.4314   2.560  0.01047 *
## RoundRound 2     1.0287    0.4512   2.280  0.02259 *
```

```
## RoundRound 3          1.2126      0.4303   2.818  0.00483 **
## PlotTreatment:RoundRound 2 -0.5905      0.5280  -1.118  0.26339
## PlotTreatment:RoundRound 3 -0.7676      0.5064  -1.516  0.12955
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Zero-inflation model:
##           Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept) -0.6196      0.2582   -2.4  0.0164 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
# Without Round as an Interaction (for comparison in anova)
Osmia_Abund_ZI_1a <- glmmTMB(Count ~ Plot + Round + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
                             ziformula = ~1 , family = "poisson",
                             data=Abundance_Osmia_1)
anova(Osmia_Abund_ZI_1, Osmia_Abund_ZI_1a)
```

```
## Data: Abundance_Osmia_1
## Models:
## Osmia_Abund_ZI_1a: Count ~ Plot + Round + (1 | `Orchard ID`/Site), zi=-1, disp=-1
## Osmia_Abund_ZI_1: Count ~ Plot * Round + (1 | `Orchard ID`/Site), zi=-1, disp=-1
##           Df    AIC    BIC logLik deviance Chisq Chi Df Pr(>Chisq)
## Osmia_Abund_ZI_1a  7 450.26 471.05 -218.13  436.26
## Osmia_Abund_ZI_1   9 451.90 478.63 -216.95  433.90 2.3649      2    0.3065
```

```
#Interaction NS.
```

```
# Test significance of Round term:
Osmia_Abund_ZI_1b <- glmmTMB(Count ~ Plot + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
                             ziformula = ~1 , family = "poisson",
                             data=Abundance_Osmia_1)
anova(Osmia_Abund_ZI_1b, Osmia_Abund_ZI_1a)
```

```
## Data: Abundance_Osmia_1
## Models:
## Osmia_Abund_ZI_1b: Count ~ Plot + (1 | `Orchard ID`/Site), zi=-1, disp=-1
## Osmia_Abund_ZI_1a: Count ~ Plot + Round + (1 | `Orchard ID`/Site), zi=-1, disp=-1
##           Df    AIC    BIC logLik deviance Chisq Chi Df Pr(>Chisq)
## Osmia_Abund_ZI_1b  5 456.50 471.35 -223.25  446.50
## Osmia_Abund_ZI_1a  7 450.26 471.05 -218.13  436.26 10.233      2    0.005998 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
# Sums by plot (treatment) and site for all flower visitors
Total_Abundance_by_Site <- Abundance_Total_1 %>%
  group_by(Site, Plot) %>%
  dplyr::summarize_at(vars(Count), list(Total_Abd=sum))
Total_Abundance_by_Site
```

1.2 All Flower Visitors

```
## # A tibble: 48 x 3
## # Groups:   Site [24]
##   Site Plot      Total_Abd
##   <chr> <chr>      <dbl>
## 1 CO_1 Control      84
## 2 CO_1 Treatment  115
## 3 FO_3 Control  142
## 4 FO_3 Treatment 328
## 5 HA_1 Control   29
## 6 HA_1 Treatment  90
## 7 HA_2 Control   76
## 8 HA_2 Treatment 167
## 9 HA_3 Control   64
## 10 HA_3 Treatment 100
## # i 38 more rows
```

```
# Means by plot (treatment) for all flower visitors
Total_Abundance_by_Plot <- Total_Abundance_by_Site %>%
  group_by(Plot) %>%
  dplyr::summarize_at(vars(Total_Abd), list(Mean_Totals=mean, SE_Totals = se))
Total_Abundance_by_Plot
```

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 3
##   Plot      Mean_Totals SE_Totals
##   <chr>      <dbl>      <dbl>
## 1 Control      155.      23.8
## 2 Treatment    185.      19.9
```

```
# Overall Percent Difference in flower visitor numbers
Total_Abundance_by_Plot %>%
  summarise(percent_diff = ((Mean_Totals[2]-Mean_Totals[1])/mean(Mean_Totals)))
```

```
##   percent_diff
## 1      0.1759725
```

```
# Mean Percent Difference across Sites
Abundance_Total_Values_Percent_Diff_by_Site <- pivot_wider(Total_Abundance_by_Site, names_from = Plot,
Abundance_Total_Values_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Diff <- Abundance_Total_Values_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Treatment
Abundance_Total_Values_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Mean_Abd <- (Abundance_Total_Values_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Tr
Abundance_Total_Values_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Percent_Diff <- 100*Abundance_Total_Values_Percent_Diff_by_
Abundance_Total_Values_Percent_Diff_by_Site
```

```
## # A tibble: 24 x 6
## # Groups:   Site [24]
##   Site Control Treatment Diff Mean_Abd Percent_Diff
##   <chr> <dbl>      <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>      <dbl>
## 1 CO_1      84      115    31    99.5      31.2
## 2 FO_3     142     328   186   235       79.1
## 3 HA_1      29      90    61    59.5     103.
## 4 HA_2      76     167    91   122.      74.9
```

```
## 5 HA_3      64      100   36   82      43.9
## 6 HC_1     215      190  -25  202.     -12.3
## 7 KO_1      89      226  137  158.     87.0
## 8 LC_1     173       52 -121  112.    -108.
## 9 MA_1     134      184   50  159     31.4
## 10 MA_2    119      169   50  144     34.7
## # i 14 more rows
```

```
mean(Abundance_Total_Values_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Percent_Diff)
```

```
## [1] 22.42953
```

```
# Is there a different between control and treatment plots for total flower-visitor abundance, and does
```

```
#First look at data distribution:
```

```
hist(Abundance_Total_1$Count)
```

Histogram of Abundance_Total_1\$Count

1.2.1 Models

Abundance_Total_1\$Count

```
#Initial model (Poisson):
```

```
Total_Abund_GLMM_1 <- glmer(Count ~ Plot * Round + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
                             family=poisson(link = "log"),
                             data=Abundance_Total_1)
```

```
# Model diagnostics:
```

```
overdisp.glmer(Total_Abund_GLMM_1)
```

```
## Residual deviance: 4183.357 on 136 degrees of freedom (ratio: 30.76)
```

```
testDispersion(Total_Abund_GLMM_1)
```



```
##  
## DHARMa nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.  
## simulated  
##  
## data: simulationOutput  
## dispersion = 3.8808, p-value < 2.2e-16  
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
simulationOutput <- simulateResiduals(fittedModel = Total_Abund_GLMM_1, plot = F)  
plot(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA residual


```
testZeroInflation(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA zero-inflation test via comparison to expected zeros with simulation under H_0 = fitted model

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p -value (two.sided) = 1

```
##
## DHARMA zero-inflation test via comparison to expected zeros with
## simulation under H0 = fitted model
##
## data: simulationOutput
## ratioObsSim = NaN, p-value = 1
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

#Serious overdispersion problem here, but not zero-inflation, so try negative binomial model fit instead

```
#Negative binomial using glmmTMB:
Total_Abund_NB_1 <- glmmTMB(Count ~ Plot*Round + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
  family = nbinom1,
  data=Abundance_Total_1)
```

```
#Diagnostics
testDispersion(Total_Abund_NB_1)
```

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 0.104

```
##
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.
## simulated
##
## data: simulationOutput
## dispersion = 1.3521, p-value = 0.104
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
simulationOutput <- simulateResiduals(fittedModel = Total_Abund_NB_1, plot = F)
plot(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA residual


```
#Results of selected model:
summary(Total_Abund_NB_1)
```

```
## Family: nbinom1 ( log )
## Formula:      Count ~ Plot * Round + (1 | 'Orchard ID'/Site)
## Data: Abundance_Total_1
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
##  1447.4   1474.1   -714.7  1429.4    135
##
## Random effects:
##
## Conditional model:
## Groups      Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## Site:'Orchard ID' (Intercept) 4.437e-09 6.661e-05
## Orchard ID   (Intercept) 2.343e-02 1.531e-01
## Number of obs: 144, groups: Site:'Orchard ID', 26; Orchard ID, 16
##
## Dispersion parameter for nbinom1 family (): 40.8
##
## Conditional model:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      4.0064494  0.1615749  24.796  <2e-16 ***
## PlotTreatment    0.4980052  0.1971185   2.526  0.0115 *
```

```
## RoundRound 2          -0.2422101  0.2210378  -1.096  0.2732
## RoundRound 3          0.0009493  0.2128714   0.004  0.9964
## PlotTreatment:RoundRound 2 -0.7461005  0.3060751  -2.438  0.0148 *
## PlotTreatment:RoundRound 3 -0.4306335  0.2854624  -1.509  0.1314
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
# Without Round as an Interaction (for comparison in anova)
Total_Abund_NB_1a <- glmmTMB(Count ~ Plot + Round + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
                             family = nbinom1,
                             data=Abundance_Total_1)
#Test significance of interaction term:
anova(Total_Abund_NB_1, Total_Abund_NB_1a)
```

```
## Data: Abundance_Total_1
## Models:
## Total_Abund_NB_1a: Count ~ Plot + Round + (1 | `Orchard ID`/Site), zi=-0, disp=~1
## Total_Abund_NB_1: Count ~ Plot * Round + (1 | `Orchard ID`/Site), zi=-0, disp=~1
##              Df    AIC    BIC logLik deviance Chisq Chi Df Pr(>Chisq)
## Total_Abund_NB_1a  7 1449.5 1470.3 -717.74  1435.5
## Total_Abund_NB_1   9 1447.4 1474.1 -714.68  1429.4 6.1267    2  0.04673 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
# Test significance of Round term:
Total_Abund_NB_1b <- glmmTMB(Count ~ Plot + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
                             family = nbinom1,
                             data=Abundance_Total_1)
anova(Total_Abund_NB_1b, Total_Abund_NB_1a)
```

```
## Data: Abundance_Total_1
## Models:
## Total_Abund_NB_1b: Count ~ Plot + (1 | `Orchard ID`/Site), zi=-0, disp=~1
## Total_Abund_NB_1a: Count ~ Plot + Round + (1 | `Orchard ID`/Site), zi=-0, disp=~1
##              Df    AIC    BIC logLik deviance Chisq Chi Df Pr(>Chisq)
## Total_Abund_NB_1b  5 1461.4 1476.3 -725.72  1451.4
## Total_Abund_NB_1a  7 1449.5 1470.3 -717.74  1435.5 15.952    2  0.0003437
##
## Total_Abund_NB_1b
## Total_Abund_NB_1a ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
# Sums by plot (treatment) and site for all flower visitors EXCLUDING APIS AND BOMBUS
Select_Abundance_by_Site <- Abundance_Select_1 %>%
  group_by(Site, Plot) %>%
  dplyr::summarize_at(vars(Count), list(Total_Abd=sum))
Select_Abundance_by_Site
```

1.3 Small Flower Visitors

```
## # A tibble: 48 x 3
## # Groups:   Site [24]
##   Site Plot      Total_Abd
##   <chr> <chr>      <dbl>
## 1 CO_1 Control      42
## 2 CO_1 Treatment    22
## 3 FO_3 Control     96
## 4 FO_3 Treatment   73
## 5 HA_1 Control     11
## 6 HA_1 Treatment   42
## 7 HA_2 Control     48
## 8 HA_2 Treatment  128
## 9 HA_3 Control     19
## 10 HA_3 Treatment   31
## # i 38 more rows
```

```
# Means by plot (treatment)
```

```
Select_Abundance_by_Plot <- Select_Abundance_by_Site %>%
  group_by(Plot) %>%
  dplyr::summarize_at(vars(Total_Abd), list(Mean_Totals=mean, SE_Totals = se))
Select_Abundance_by_Plot
```

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 3
##   Plot      Mean_Totals SE_Totals
##   <chr>      <dbl>      <dbl>
## 1 Control      67.6        7.86
## 2 Treatment    79.3       12.7
```

```
# Overall Percent Difference
```

```
Select_Abundance_by_Plot %>%
  summarise(percent_diff = ((Mean_Totals[2]-Mean_Totals[1])/mean(Mean_Totals)))
```

```
##   percent_diff
## 1    0.1599546
```

```
# Mean Percent Difference across Sites
```

```
Abundance_Select_Values_Percent_Diff_by_Site <- pivot_wider(Select_Abundance_by_Site, names_from = Plot
Abundance_Select_Values_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Diff <- Abundance_Select_Values_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Treatm
Abundance_Select_Values_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Mean_Abd <- (Abundance_Select_Values_Percent_Diff_by_Site$
Abundance_Select_Values_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Percent_Diff <- 100*Abundance_Select_Values_Percent_Diff_b
Abundance_Select_Values_Percent_Diff_by_Site
```

```
## # A tibble: 24 x 6
## # Groups:   Site [24]
##   Site Control Treatment Diff Mean_Abd Percent_Diff
##   <chr> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 CO_1 42 22 -20 32 -62.5
## 2 FO_3 96 73 -23 84.5 -27.2
## 3 HA_1 11 42 31 26.5 117.
## 4 HA_2 48 128 80 88 90.9
## 5 HA_3 19 31 12 25 48
## 6 HC_1 86 20 -66 53 -125.
```

```
## 7 KO_1      33      76  43   54.5    78.9
## 8 LC_1      78      28 -50   53    -94.3
## 9 MA_1     105     160  55  132.    41.5
## 10 MA_2     85     142  57  114.    50.2
## # i 14 more rows
```

```
mean(Abundance_Select_Values_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Percent_Diff)
```

```
## [1] 12.57634
```

```
# Is there a different between control and treatment plots for small flower-visitor abundance, and does
```

```
#First look at data distribution:
```

```
hist(Abundance_Select_1$Count)
```

Histogram of Abundance_Select_1\$Count

1.3.1 Models

Abundance_Select_1\$Count

```
#Initial model (Poisson):
```

```
Select_Abund_GLMM_1 <- glmer(Count ~ Plot*Round + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
                             family=poisson(link = "log"),
                             data=Abundance_Select_1)
```

```
# Model diagnostics:
```

```
overdisp.glmer(Select_Abund_GLMM_1)
```

```
## Residual deviance: 2320.876 on 136 degrees of freedom (ratio: 17.065)
```

```
testDispersion(Select_Abund_GLMM_1)
```

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 0

```
##  
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.  
## simulated  
##  
## data: simulationOutput  
## dispersion = 4.1427, p-value < 2.2e-16  
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
simulationOutput <- simulateResiduals(fittedModel = Select_Abund_GLMM_1, plot = F)  
plot(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA residual


```
testZeroInflation(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA zero-inflation test via comparison to expected zeros with simulation under H_0 = fitted model


```
##
## DHARMA zero-inflation test via comparison to expected zeros with
## simulation under H0 = fitted model
##
## data: simulationOutput
## ratioObsSim = 83.333, p-value < 2.2e-16
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

#Some problems here, so try zero-inflated model fit instead.

```
#Zero-inflated Poisson using glmmTMB:
Select_Abund_ZI_1 <- glmmTMB(Count ~ Plot*Round + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
  ziformula = ~1 , family = "poisson",
  data=Abundance_Select_1)
```

```
#Diagnostics
testDispersion(Select_Abund_ZI_1)
```

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 0.024

```
##
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.
## simulated
##
## data: simulationOutput
## dispersion = 3.3769, p-value = 0.024
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
simulationOutput <- simulateResiduals(fittedModel = Select_Abund_ZI_1, plot = F)
plot(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA residual

#Still some issues, but not as bad.

#Negative binomial using glmmTMB:

```
Select_Abund_NB_1 <- glmmTMB(Count ~ Plot*Round + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
  family = nbinom1,
  data=Abundance_Select_1)
```

#Diagnostics

```
testDispersion(Select_Abund_NB_1)
```

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 0.024

```
##  
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.  
## simulated  
##  
## data: simulationOutput  
## dispersion = 1.727, p-value = 0.024  
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
simulationOutput <- simulateResiduals(fittedModel = Select_Abund_NB_1, plot = F)  
plot(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA residual

#Much better, though still some overdispersion.

#Results of selected model:
`summary(Select_Abund_NB_1)`

```
## Family: nbinom1 ( log )
## Formula: Count ~ Plot * Round + (1 | 'Orchard ID'/Site)
## Data: Abundance_Select_1
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 1219.9 1246.7  -601.0  1201.9    135
##
## Random effects:
##
## Conditional model:
## Groups      Name      Variance Std.Dev.
## Site:'Orchard ID' (Intercept) 1.841e-09 4.291e-05
## Orchard ID   (Intercept) 6.887e-02 2.624e-01
## Number of obs: 144, groups: Site:'Orchard ID', 26; Orchard ID, 16
##
## Dispersion parameter for nbinom1 family (): 20.9
##
## Conditional model:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      2.8744    0.2016 14.256  <2e-16 ***
## PlotTreatment     0.4491    0.2360  1.903  0.0571 .
## RoundRound 2     0.2386    0.2424  0.984  0.3249
## RoundRound 3     0.3330    0.2384  1.397  0.1625
```

```
## PlotTreatment:RoundRound 2 -0.6678 0.3337 -2.001 0.0454 *
## PlotTreatment:RoundRound 3 -0.3683 0.3191 -1.154 0.2484
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
#Negative binomial without interaction, to test significance:
Select_Abund_NB_1a <- glmmTMB(Count ~ Plot + Round + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
                             family = nbinom1,
                             data=Abundance_Select_1)
anova(Select_Abund_NB_1a, Select_Abund_NB_1)
```

```
## Data: Abundance_Select_1
## Models:
## Select_Abund_NB_1a: Count ~ Plot + Round + (1 | `Orchard ID`/Site), zi=~0, disp=~1
## Select_Abund_NB_1: Count ~ Plot * Round + (1 | `Orchard ID`/Site), zi=~0, disp=~1
##           Df AIC BIC logLik deviance Chisq Chi Df Pr(>Chisq)
## Select_Abund_NB_1a 7 1220 1240.7 -602.97 1206
## Select_Abund_NB_1 9 1220 1246.7 -600.97 1202 3.9987 2 0.1354
```

```
#Interaction NS.
```

```
# Test significance of Round term:
Select_Abund_NB_1b <- glmmTMB(Count ~ Plot + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
                              family = nbinom1,
                              data=Abundance_Select_1)
anova(Select_Abund_NB_1b, Select_Abund_NB_1a)
```

```
## Data: Abundance_Select_1
## Models:
## Select_Abund_NB_1b: Count ~ Plot + (1 | `Orchard ID`/Site), zi=~0, disp=~1
## Select_Abund_NB_1a: Count ~ Plot + Round + (1 | `Orchard ID`/Site), zi=~0, disp=~1
##           Df AIC BIC logLik deviance Chisq Chi Df Pr(>Chisq)
## Select_Abund_NB_1b 5 1218.4 1233.3 -604.20 1208.4
## Select_Abund_NB_1a 7 1220.0 1240.7 -602.97 1206.0 2.4604 2 0.2922
```

```
#Round NS.
```

2. Apple Yield and Quality

```
# Mean and SE of fruit-set pre-thinning values per plot
Apple_Values_Pre <- Apple_1 %>%
  group_by(Plot) %>%
  dplyr::summarize(Mean_Fruit_Set_Pre=mean(Fruit_Set_Pre),
                  SE_Fruit_Set_Pre=se(Fruit_Set_Pre))
Apple_Values_Pre
```

2.1 Pre- and Post-Thinning Fruit Set

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 3
##   Plot      Mean_Fruit_Set_Pre SE_Fruit_Set_Pre
##   <chr>          <dbl>          <dbl>
## 1 Control          0.465          0.0301
## 2 Treatment        0.503          0.0302
```

```
# Mean and SE of fruit set post-thinning per plot
Apple_Post_Values <- Apple_1 %>%
  group_by(Plot) %>%
  dplyr::summarize(Mean_Fruit_Set_Post = mean(Fruit_Set_Post),
                  SE_Fruit_Set_Post = se(Fruit_Set_Post))
Apple_Post_Values
```

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 3
##   Plot      Mean_Fruit_Set_Post SE_Fruit_Set_Post
##   <chr>          <dbl>          <dbl>
## 1 Control          0.0834          0.0159
## 2 Treatment        0.0935          0.0145
```

```
hist(Apple_1$Fruit_Set_Pre)
```

Histogram of Apple_1\$Fruit_Set_Pre

2.1.1 Pre-Thinning Model

Apple_1\$Fruit_Set_Pre

```
hist(Apple_1$Pre_Fruit)
```

Histogram of Apple_1\$Pre_Fruit


```
# Binomial GLMER With Site as a Random Effect
Apple_Pre_Thin_GLM <- glmer(cbind(Pre_Fruit,Buds) ~ Plot + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
                           family = binomial(link = "logit"),
                           data=Apple_1)
summary(Apple_Pre_Thin_GLM)
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: cbind(Pre_Fruit, Buds) ~ Plot + (1 | `Orchard ID`/Site)
## Data: Apple_1
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 2001.8   2013.7  -996.9   1993.8     140
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -10.5333  -1.2928  -0.0399   1.2446   6.4893
##
## Random effects:
## Groups           Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## Site:`Orchard ID` (Intercept) 0.1175   0.3428
## Orchard ID       (Intercept) 0.0230   0.1517
## Number of obs: 144, groups: Site:`Orchard ID`, 26; Orchard ID, 16
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)  -0.83342   0.08489  -9.818  <2e-16 ***
## PlotTreatment 0.02287    0.02138   1.069   0.285
```

```
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##      (Intr)
## PlotTretmnt -0.147
```

```
# Model diagnostics:
overdisp.glmmer(Apple_Pre_Thin_GLM)
```

```
## Residual deviance: 1161.945 on 140 degrees of freedom (ratio: 8.3)
```

```
testDispersion(Apple_Pre_Thin_GLM)
```


Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 0.08

```
##
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.
## simulated
##
## data:  simulationOutput
## dispersion = 1.3736, p-value = 0.08
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
simulationOutput <- simulateResiduals(fittedModel = Apple_Pre_Thin_GLM, plot = T)
```

DHARMA residual

#Fit isn't great.

#Ordered beta regression with Site random:

```
Apple_Pre_Thin_GLM <- glmmTMB(Fruit_Set_Pre ~ Plot + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
                             dispformula = ~1,
                             family = ordbeta,
                             data=Apple_1)
summary(Apple_Pre_Thin_GLM)
```

```
## Family: ordbeta ( logit )
## Formula:      Fruit_Set_Pre ~ Plot + (1 | `Orchard ID`/Site)
## Data: Apple_1
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
##    18.0    38.7    -2.0     4.0     137
##
## Random effects:
##
## Conditional model:
## Groups      Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## Site:`Orchard ID` (Intercept) 0.2215  0.4706
## Orchard ID   (Intercept) 0.1147  0.3386
## Number of obs: 144, groups: Site:`Orchard ID`, 26; Orchard ID, 16
##
## Dispersion parameter for ordbeta family (): 5.83
##
## Conditional model:
##           Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
```

```
## (Intercept) -0.08702  0.16577 -0.525  0.60
## PlotTreatment 0.10920  0.13555  0.806  0.42
```

```
# Model diagnostics:
testDispersion(Apple_Pre_Thin_GLM)
```


Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 1

```
##
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.
## simulated
##
## data: simulationOutput
## dispersion = 1, p-value = 1
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
simulationOutput <- simulateResiduals(fittedModel = Apple_Pre_Thin_GLM, plot = F)
plot(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA residual

#Also not great, but same conclusion.

With Site as a Random Effect

```
hist(Apple_1$Fruit_Set_Post)
```

Histogram of Apple_1\$Fruit_Set_Post

2.1.2 Post-Thinning Model

```
# Binomial GLMER With Site as a Random Effect
```

```
Apple_Post_Thin_GLM <- glmer(Post_Fruit/Buds ~ Plot + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
                             family = binomial(link = "logit"),
                             data=Apple_1)
summary(Apple_Post_Thin_GLM)
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: Post_Fruit/Buds ~ Plot + (1 | `Orchard ID`/Site)
## Data: Apple_1
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
##  44.6    56.4   -18.3   36.6     140
##
## Scaled residuals:
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -0.1690 -0.1690  0.0512  0.6063  3.8177
##
## Random effects:
## Groups           Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## Site:`Orchard ID` (Intercept) 0         0
## Orchard ID       (Intercept) 0         0
## Number of obs: 144, groups: Site:`Orchard ID`, 26; Orchard ID, 16
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept) -3.555e+00  7.171e-01 -4.958 7.13e-07 ***
```

```
## PlotTreatment 1.168e-06 1.014e+00 0.000 1
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
## (Intr)
## PlotTretmnt -0.707
## optimizer (Nelder_Mead) convergence code: 0 (OK)
## boundary (singular) fit: see help('isSingular')
```

```
# Model diagnostics:
overdisp.glmer(Apple_Post_Thin_GLM)
```

```
## Residual deviance: 36.854 on 140 degrees of freedom (ratio: 0.263)
```

```
testDispersion(Apple_Post_Thin_GLM)
```


Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 0.52

```
##
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.
## simulated
##
## data: simulationOutput
## dispersion = 0.61208, p-value = 0.52
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
simulationOutput <- simulateResiduals(fittedModel = Apple_Post_Thin_GLM, plot = T)
```

DHARMA residual

#Fit is terrible.

#Ordered beta regression with Site random:

```
Apple_Post_Thin_GLM <- glmmTMB(Fruit_Set_Post ~ Plot + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
                               dispformula = ~1,
                               family = ordbeta,
                               data=Apple_1)
summary(Apple_Post_Thin_GLM)
```

```
## Family: ordbeta ( logit )
## Formula:      Fruit_Set_Post ~ Plot + (1 | `Orchard ID`/Site)
## Data: Apple_1
##
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
##    -18.1      2.6     16.1   -32.1     137
##
## Random effects:
##
## Conditional model:
## Groups      Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## Site:`Orchard ID` (Intercept) 0.09651  0.3107
## Orchard ID   (Intercept) 0.18448  0.4295
## Number of obs: 144, groups: Site:`Orchard ID`, 26; Orchard ID, 16
##
## Dispersion parameter for ordbeta family (): 7.68
```

```
##
## Conditional model:
##           Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)  -2.1926    0.2134 -10.273  <2e-16 ***
## PlotTreatment  0.1223    0.1646   0.743   0.457
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
# Model diagnostics:
testDispersion(Apple_Post_Thin_GLM)
```

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 1

```
##
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.
## simulated
##
## data: simulationOutput
## dispersion = 1, p-value = 1
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
simulationOutput <- simulateResiduals(fittedModel = Apple_Post_Thin_GLM, plot = F)
plot(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA residual

#Not great, but much better.

```
#First summarizing by treatment within sites:
Apple_1_site_summary <- Apple_1 %>%
  group_by(Plot, Site) %>%
  dplyr::summarize(circum = mean(Mean_Circum, na.rm = T),
                  count = n())
Apple_1_site_summary
```

2.3 Apple Quality

```
## # A tibble: 48 x 4
## # Groups:   Plot [2]
##   Plot Site circum count
##   <chr> <chr> <dbl> <int>
## 1 Control CO_1 32.5 3
## 2 Control FO_3 23.7 3
## 3 Control HA_1 20 3
## 4 Control HA_2 13.5 3
## 5 Control HA_3 9.17 3
## 6 Control HC_1 NaN 3
## 7 Control KO_1 16.8 3
## 8 Control LC_1 17 3
## 9 Control MA_1 NaN 3
## 10 Control MA_2 30 3
## # i 38 more rows
```

```

#Then summarizing by treatment across sites
Apple_1_site_summary <- Apple_1_site_summary %>%
  group_by(Plot) %>%
  dplyr::summarize(mean = mean(circum, na.rm = T),
                  SE = se(circum),
                  count = n())
Apple_1_site_summary

```

```

## # A tibble: 2 x 4
##   Plot      mean    SE count
##   <chr>    <dbl> <dbl> <int>
## 1 Control    19.0  1.21   24
## 2 Treatment  17.6  1.18   24

```

```

#How many trees with non-zero values in each treatment?
dim(subset(subset(Apple_1, `Fruits Measured`>0), Plot == "Treatment"))

```

```
## [1] 51 41
```

```
dim(subset(subset(Apple_1, `Fruits Measured`>0), Plot == "Control"))
```

```
## [1] 47 41
```

```

#Distribution
hist(Apple_1$Mean_Circum)

```

Histogram of Apple_1\$Mean_Circum

2.3.1 Models

```

# With Site as a Random Effect
Apple_Quality_LMM <- lmer(Mean_Circum ~ Plot + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
                          data=Apple_1)
summary(Apple_Quality_LMM)

## Linear mixed model fit by REML. t-tests use Satterthwaite's method [
## lmerModLmerTest]
## Formula: Mean_Circum ~ Plot + (1 | `Orchard ID`/Site)
## Data: Apple_1
##
## REML criterion at convergence: 611.1
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -2.19481 -0.54152  0.01032  0.53490  2.69397
##
## Random effects:
## Groups          Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## Site: `Orchard ID` (Intercept)  3.021   1.738
## Orchard ID       (Intercept)  9.513   3.084
## Residual                    25.234   5.023
## Number of obs: 98, groups: Site: `Orchard ID`, 24; Orchard ID, 15
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error   df t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)    19.361     1.219  9.927  15.887 2.19e-08 ***
## PlotTreatment  -1.822     1.064 84.116  -1.713  0.0903 .
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr)
## PlotTretmnt -0.479

# Assumptions
overdisp.glmer(Apple_Quality_LMM)

## Residual deviance: 2111.115 on 94 degrees of freedom (ratio: 22.459)

testDispersion(Apple_Quality_LMM)

```

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 0.8

```
##  
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.  
## simulated  
##  
## data: simulationOutput  
## dispersion = 0.932, p-value = 0.8  
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
simulationOutput <- simulateResiduals(fittedModel = Apple_Quality_LMM, plot = T)
```

DHARMA residual

#All looks good.

Data Organization: Year 2

1. Flower-Visitor Abundance

```
# Loading Excel file (Year 2)
Abundance_Total_Y2 <- read_excel("Total_Abundance_Year_2.xlsx")

# Merging variable names to create unique identifiers for every site
Abundance_Total_2 <- Abundance_Total_Y2 %>% unite('Site', Orchard, `Site ID`, remove = FALSE)

# Adding Year column
Abundance_Total_2 <- Abundance_Total_2 %>% add_column(Year = 2022)

# Only look at Osmia
Abundance_Osmia_2 <- Abundance_Total_2 %>% filter(Taxa == "Osmia")

# Summarizing *Osmia* counts per transect walk:
Abundance_Osmia_2 <- Abundance_Osmia_2 %>% group_by(Plot, Site, `Orchard ID`, Year) %>%
  summarise_at(vars(Count), list(Count=sum))

# Extract observations from apple bloom of Year 1 and reorganize to match Year 2:
Abundance_Osmia_Y1_AB <- Abundance_Osmia_1 %>% filter(Round == "Apple Bloom") %>% add_column(Year = 2022)
Abundance_Osmia_Y1_AB <- Abundance_Osmia_Y1_AB[,c(1,4,2,6,5)]
```

```
# Combine both years (apple bloom period only):
Abundance_Osmia_AB <- rbind(Abundance_Osmia_Y1_AB, Abundance_Osmia_2)
```

1.1 *Osmia* spp. Abundance

```
# Loading Excel file (Year 2)
Abundance_Total_2 <- read_excel("Total_Abundance_Year_2.xlsx")

# Merging variable names to create unique identifiers for every site
Abundance_Total_2 <- Abundance_Total_2 %>% unite('Site', Orchard, `Site ID`, remove = FALSE)

# Adding Year column
Abundance_Total_2 <- Abundance_Total_2 %>% add_column(Year = 2022)

# Summarizing Flower visitor counts counts per transect walk
Abundance_Total_2 %>% group_by(Taxa) %>%
  summarise_at(vars(Count), list(Count=sum))

# Summarizing pollinator counts per transect walk and adding Year column:
Abundance_Total_2 <- Abundance_Total_2 %>% group_by(Plot, Site, `Orchard ID`, Year) %>%
  summarise_at(vars(Count), list(Count=sum))

# Extract observations from apple bloom of Year 1 and reorganize to match Year 2:
Abundance_Total_Y1_AB <- Abundance_Total_1 %>% filter(Round == "Apple Bloom") %>% add_column(Year = 2022)
Abundance_Total_Y1_AB <- Abundance_Total_Y1_AB[,c(1,4,2,6,5)]

# Combine both years (apple bloom period only):
Abundance_Total_AB <- rbind(Abundance_Total_Y1_AB, Abundance_Total_2)
```

1.2 All Flower Visitors

```
# Loading Excel file (Year 2)
Abundance_Select_Y2 <- read_excel("Total_Abundance_Year_2.xlsx")

# Merging variable names to create unique identifiers for every site
Abundance_Select_2 <- Abundance_Select_Y2 %>% unite('Site', Orchard, `Site ID`, remove = FALSE)

# Adding Year column
Abundance_Select_2 <- Abundance_Select_2 %>% add_column(Year = 2022)

# Exclude Apis and Bombus
Abundance_Select_2 <- Abundance_Select_2 %>% filter(Taxa != "Apis", Taxa != "Bombus", Taxa != "Bombus Q")

# Summarizing small insect counts per transect walk:
Abundance_Select_2 <- Abundance_Select_2 %>% group_by(Plot, Site, `Orchard ID`, Year) %>%
  summarise_at(vars(Count), list(Count=sum))
```

```

# Extract observations from apple bloom of Year 1 and reorganize to match Year 2:
Abundance_Select_Y1_AB <- Abundance_Select_1 %>% filter(Round == "Apple Bloom") %>% add_column(Year = 2021)
Abundance_Select_Y1_AB <- Abundance_Select_Y1_AB[,c(1,4,2,6,5)]

# Combine both years (apple bloom period only):
Abundance_Select_AB <- rbind(Abundance_Select_Y1_AB, Abundance_Select_2)

```

1.3 Small Flower Visitors

1.4 All Years and Rounds (for Plotting)

```

# Add columns for year and round, and reorganize for years to match:
Abundance_Osmia_1 <- Abundance_Osmia_1 %>% add_column(Year = 2021)
Abundance_Osmia_1 <- Abundance_Osmia_1 %>%
  relocate(Site, .after = Plot)
Abundance_Osmia_2 <- Abundance_Osmia_2 %>% add_column(Round = "Apple Bloom")
Abundance_Osmia_2 <- Abundance_Osmia_2 %>%
  relocate(Round, .after = `Orchard ID`)

# Bind Osmia Year 1 and Year 2 Data
Abundance_Osmia_All <- rbind(Abundance_Osmia_1, Abundance_Osmia_2)
Abundance_Osmia_All <- Abundance_Osmia_All %>% add_column(Taxa = "Osmia")

# Rename columns
Abundance_Osmia_All$Round <- factor(Abundance_Osmia_All$Round, levels=c("Apple Bloom", "Round 2", "Round 3"))
Abundance_Osmia_All$Round_Year <- paste(Abundance_Osmia_All$Round, Abundance_Osmia_All$Year, sep = " ")

```

1.4.1 *Osmia* spp.

```

# Add columns for year and round, and reorganize for years to match:
Abundance_Total_1 <- Abundance_Total_1 %>% add_column(Year = 2021)
Abundance_Total_1 <- Abundance_Total_1 %>%
  relocate(Site, .after = Plot)
Abundance_Total_2 <- Abundance_Total_2 %>% add_column(Round = "Apple Bloom")
Abundance_Total_2 <- Abundance_Total_2 %>%
  relocate(Round, .after = `Orchard ID`)

# Bind Year 1 and Year 2 Data
Abundance_Total_All <- rbind(Abundance_Total_1, Abundance_Total_2)
Abundance_Total_All <- Abundance_Total_All %>% add_column(Taxa = "All")

# Rename columns
Abundance_Total_All$Round <- factor(Abundance_Total_All$Round, levels=c("Apple Bloom", "Round 2", "Round 3"))
Abundance_Total_All$Round_Year <- paste(Abundance_Total_All$Round, Abundance_Total_All$Year, sep = " ")

```

1.4.2 All Flower Visitors

2. Apple Yield and Quality

```
# Loading Excel File
Apple_2 <- read_excel("Apple_Year_2.xlsx", na = "N/A")

# Merging variable names (Orchard (the logistical orchard name according to orchard pairings) and Site
Apple_2 <- Apple_2 %>% unite('Site', `Orchard`, `Site ID`, remove = FALSE)

# Creating columns for total fruit and bud numbers per tree (N + S branches)
Apple_2$Buds <- Apple_2`N Bud #` + Apple_2`S Bud #`
Apple_2$Pre_Fruit <- Apple_2`N Pre-Thinning Fruit #` + Apple_2`S Pre-Thinning Fruit #`

# Calculating fruit set pre-thinning
Apple_2$Fruit_Set_Pre <- Apple_2$Pre_Fruit/Apple_2$Buds
```

2.1 Pre-Thinning

```
Apple_1 <- Apple_1 %>% add_column(Year = 2021)
Apple_2 <- Apple_2 %>% add_column(Year = 2022)
Apple_All <- bind_rows(Apple_1, Apple_2)
```

2.2 All Years

Results: Year 2

1. Flower-Visitor Abundance

```
# Calculating means for Osmia values for both years (apple bloom period only):
Abundance_Osmia_Summary <- Abundance_Osmia_AB %>%
  group_by(Plot) %>%
  dplyr::summarize_at(vars(Count), list(Mean_Count = mean, SE_Count = se))
Abundance_Osmia_Summary
```

1.1 *Osmiaspp.* Abundance

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 3
##   Plot      Mean_Count SE_Count
##   <chr>      <dbl>    <dbl>
## 1 Control    0.958    0.289
## 2 Treatment  3.44     0.983
```

```
# Percent Difference between treatments
Abundance_Osmia_Summary %>%
  summarise(percent_diff = (100*(Mean_Count[2]-Mean_Count[1])/mean(Mean_Count)))
```

```
## percent_diff
## 1 112.7962
```

```
# Mean and SE of Percent Difference between Site pairs, both Years:
# Note that this is unreliable because of a lot of 0 values generating NAs.
```

```
Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site <- pivot_wider(Abundance_Osmia_AB[,c(-3)], id_cols=c(Site, Year),
Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Diff <- Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Treatment - Abundance
Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Mean_Abd <- (Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Treatment+Abundan
Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Percent_Diff <- 100*Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Diff/Abund
Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site
```

```
## # A tibble: 48 x 7
```

```
## Site Year Control Treatment Diff Mean_Abd Percent_Diff
## <chr> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 CO_1 2021 0 2 2 1 200
## 2 HA_1 2021 0 1 1 0.5 200
## 3 HA_2 2021 0 0 0 0 NaN
## 4 HA_3 2021 0 0 0 0 NaN
## 5 HC_1 2021 0 0 0 0 NaN
## 6 KO_1 2021 1 7 6 4 150
## 7 LC_1 2021 0 3 3 1.5 200
## 8 MA_1 2021 1 1 0 1 0
## 9 MA_2 2021 1 5 4 3 133.
## 10 MA_3 2021 1 0 -1 0.5 -200
## # i 38 more rows
```

```
mean(Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Percent_Diff, na.rm = T); sd(Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Percent_Diff)
```

```
## [1] 95.52888
```

```
## [1] 20.96677
```

```
# Calculating means for Osmia values for year 2
```

```
Abundance_Osmia_Y2_Summary <- Abundance_Osmia_2 %>%
  group_by(Plot) %>%
  dplyr::summarize_at(vars(Count), list(Mean_Count=mean, SE_Count = se))
Abundance_Osmia_Y2_Summary
```

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 3
```

```
## Plot Mean_Count SE_Count
## <chr> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 Control 1.54 0.545
## 2 Treatment 5.46 1.86
```

```
# Overall Percent Difference between treatments Year 2
```

```
Abundance_Osmia_Y2_Summary %>%
  summarise(percent_diff = (100*(Mean_Count[2]-Mean_Count[1])/mean(Mean_Count)))
```

```
## percent_diff
## 1 111.9048
```

```
# Mean and SE of Percent Difference between Site pairs, Year 2:
```

```
# Note that this is unreliable because of a lot of 0 values generating NAs.
```

```
Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site <- pivot_wider(Abundance_Osmia_2[,c(-3)], names_from = Plot, values_from = Abundance)
Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Diff <- Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Treatment - Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Control
Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Mean_Abd <- (Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Treatment+Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Control)/2
Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Percent_Diff <- 100*Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Diff/Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Mean_Abd
```

```
## # A tibble: 24 x 8
```

```
## # Groups:   Site [24]
```

```
##   Site Round      Year Control Treatment Diff Mean_Abd Percent_Diff
##   <chr> <chr>    <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 CO_1 Apple Bloom 2022 0 0 0 0 NaN
## 2 FO_3 Apple Bloom 2022 0 0 0 0 NaN
## 3 HA_1 Apple Bloom 2022 7 15 8 11 72.7
## 4 HA_2 Apple Bloom 2022 2 12 10 7 143.
## 5 HA_3 Apple Bloom 2022 0 1 1 0.5 200
## 6 HC_1 Apple Bloom 2022 0 8 8 4 200
## 7 KO_1 Apple Bloom 2022 8 28 20 18 111.
## 8 LC_1 Apple Bloom 2022 6 34 28 20 140
## 9 MA_1 Apple Bloom 2022 4 11 7 7.5 93.3
## 10 MA_2 Apple Bloom 2022 1 10 9 5.5 164.
## # i 14 more rows
```

```
mean(Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Percent_Diff, na.rm = T); sd(Abundance_Osmia_Percent_Diff_by_Site$Percent_Diff)
```

```
## [1] 111.2747
```

```
## [1] 23.80323
```

```
# Only Year 2
```

```
hist(Abundance_Osmia_2$Count)
```

Histogram of Abundance_Osmia_2\$Count

1.1.1 Models

Abundance_Osmia_2\$Count

```
Osmia_Abund_GLMM_Y2 <- glmer(Count ~ Plot + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),  
  family=poisson(link = "log"),  
  data=Abundance_Osmia_2)
```

```
# Model diagnostics:
```

```
overdisp.glmer(Osmia_Abund_GLMM_Y2)
```

```
## Residual deviance: 27.393 on 44 degrees of freedom (ratio: 0.623)
```

```
testDispersion(Osmia_Abund_GLMM_Y2)
```

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 0.76

```
##  
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.  
## simulated  
##  
## data: simulationOutput  
## dispersion = 0.027198, p-value = 0.76  
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
simulationOutput <- simulateResiduals(fittedModel = Osmia_Abund_GLMM_Y2, plot = F)  
plot(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA residual


```
testZeroInflation(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA zero-inflation test via comparison to expected zeros with simulation under H0 = fitted model

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 0.952

```
##
## DHARMA zero-inflation test via comparison to expected zeros with
## simulation under H0 = fitted model
##
## data: simulationOutput
## ratioObsSim = 0.9608, p-value = 0.952
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
#No problems detected.
```

```
#Results (Year 2 only):
summary(Osmia_Abund_GLMM_Y2)
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: poisson ( log )
## Formula: Count ~ Plot + (1 | 'Orchard ID'/Site)
## Data: Abundance_Osmia_2
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
##  181.7   189.2   -86.9   173.7     44
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -1.4545 -0.4878 -0.3312  0.1315  2.9460
##
## Random effects:
## Groups           Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## Site:'Orchard ID' (Intercept) 1.396    1.181
## Orchard ID       (Intercept) 3.758    1.939
## Number of obs: 48, groups: Site:'Orchard ID', 26; Orchard ID, 16
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)   -1.3251    0.6988  -1.896  0.0579 .
## PlotTreatment  1.2152    0.1880   6.465 1.02e-10 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr)
## PlotTretmnt -0.199
```

```
# Both Years, apple bloom period only, With Year as fixed categorical variable, including interaction:
```

```
Osmia_Abund_GLMM_Year_All <- glmer(Count ~ Plot * as.factor(Year) + (1|'Orchard ID'/Site),
  family=poisson(link = "log"),
  data=Abundance_Osmia_AB,
  control=glmerControl(optimizer="nloptwrap"))
```

```
# Model diagnostics:
overdisp.glmer(Osmia_Abund_GLMM_Year_All)
```

```
## Residual deviance: 128.415 on 90 degrees of freedom (ratio: 1.427)
```

```
testDispersion(Osmia_Abund_GLMM_Year_All)
```

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 0.688

```
##  
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.  
## simulated  
##  
## data: simulationOutput  
## dispersion = 0.59105, p-value = 0.688  
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
simulationOutput <- simulateResiduals(fittedModel = Osmia_Abund_GLMM_Year_All, plot = F)  
plot(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA residual


```
testZeroInflation(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA zero-inflation test via comparison to expected zeros with simulation under $H_0 =$ fitted model

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p -value (two.sided) = 0.616

```

##
## DHARMA zero-inflation test via comparison to expected zeros with
## simulation under H0 = fitted model
##
## data: simulationOutput
## ratioObsSim = 1.0766, p-value = 0.616
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided

#No problems detected.

#Results (both years):
summary(Osmia_Abund_GLMM_Year_All)

## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: poisson ( log )
## Formula: Count ~ Plot * as.factor(Year) + (1 | 'Orchard ID'/Site)
## Data: Abundance_Osmia_AB
## Control: glmerControl(optimizer = "nloptwrap")
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
##  340.5   355.9  -164.3   328.5     90
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -1.5321 -0.7421 -0.3758  0.3545  4.4876
##
## Random effects:
##  Groups           Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## Site:'Orchard ID' (Intercept) 0.8602   0.9275
## Orchard ID        (Intercept) 0.9210   0.9597
## Number of obs: 96, groups: Site:'Orchard ID', 26; Orchard ID, 16
##
## Fixed effects:
##                                     Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)                        -1.79472   0.46746  -3.839 0.000123 ***
## PlotTreatment                       1.29513   0.36784   3.521 0.000430 ***
## as.factor(Year)2022                 1.41363   0.36388   3.885 0.000102 ***
## PlotTreatment:as.factor(Year)2022 -0.06492   0.40982  -0.158 0.874140
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) PltTrt a.(Y)2
## PlotTretmnt -0.618
## as.f(Y)2022 -0.626  0.796
## PT:.(Y)2022  0.556 -0.894 -0.888
## optimizer (nloptwrap) convergence code: 0 (OK)
## Model failed to converge with max|grad| = 0.00216503 (tol = 0.002, component 1)

#Means and SEs, across the two years (48 observations):

```

```
Abundance_Total_AB %>%
  group_by(Plot) %>%
  dplyr::summarize_at(vars(Count), list(Mean_Count = mean, SE_Count = se))
```

1.2 All Flower Visitors

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 3
##   Plot      Mean_Count SE_Count
##   <chr>      <dbl>    <dbl>
## 1 Control      63.8      7.18
## 2 Treatment    102.     12.7
```

```
# Percent Diff
Abundance_Total_AB_Percent_Diff <- Abundance_Total_AB %>%
  group_by(Plot) %>%
  dplyr::summarize_at(vars(Count), list(Mean_Count = mean, SE_Count = se))

Abundance_Total_AB_Percent_Diff %>%
  summarise(percent_diff = (100*(Mean_Count[2]-Mean_Count[1])/mean(Mean_Count)))
```

```
##   percent_diff
## 1      45.90205
```

```
# Calculate mean % difference in pollinator numbers during apple bloom, both years combined.
# Orchard ID column has to be removed.
```

```
Abundance_Total_Values_Diff <- pivot_wider(Abundance_Total_AB, id_cols=c(Site, Year), names_from = Plot)
Abundance_Total_Values_Diff$Percent_Diff <- (Abundance_Total_Values_Diff$Treatment - Abundance_Total_Values_Diff$Control) / Abundance_Total_Values_Diff$Control
```

```
# Mean percent difference in pollinator abundance:
mean(Abundance_Total_Values_Diff$Percent_Diff)
```

```
## [1] 29.92832
```

```
# Std. error of percent difference in bee abundance:
```

```
sd(Abundance_Total_Values_Diff$Percent_Diff, na.rm = T) / sqrt(length(Abundance_Total_Values_Diff$Percent_Diff))
```

```
## [1] 13.36443
```

```
# With Year as Fixed categorical variable
hist(sqrt(Abundance_Total_AB$Count))
```

Histogram of sqrt(Abundance_Total_AB\$Count)

1.2.1 Models

sqrt(Abundance_Total_AB\$Count)

```
Total_Abund_GLMM_Year_All <- lmer(sqrt(Count) ~ Plot * as.factor(Year) + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),  
  data=Abundance_Total_AB)
```

```
# Model diagnostics:
```

```
overdisp.glmer(Total_Abund_GLMM_Year_All)
```

```
## Residual deviance: 1069.823 on 90 degrees of freedom (ratio: 11.887)
```

```
testDispersion(Total_Abund_GLMM_Year_All)
```

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 0.88

```
##  
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.  
## simulated  
##  
## data: simulationOutput  
## dispersion = 0.97821, p-value = 0.88  
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
simulationOutput <- simulateResiduals(fittedModel = Total_Abund_GLMM_Year_All, plot = F)  
plot(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA residual


```
#Results (both years):
summary(Total_Abund_GLMM_Year_All)
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by REML. t-tests use Satterthwaite's method [
## lmerModLmerTest]
## Formula: sqrt(Count) ~ Plot * as.factor(Year) + (1 | 'Orchard ID'/Site)
## Data: Abundance_Total_AB
##
## REML criterion at convergence: 519.9
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -1.81555 -0.49076 -0.05809  0.56435  2.38165
##
## Random effects:
## Groups          Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## Site:'Orchard ID' (Intercept)  0.1963  0.443
## Orchard ID      (Intercept)  2.5063  1.583
## Residual                            12.7659  3.573
## Number of obs: 96, groups: Site:'Orchard ID', 26; Orchard ID, 16
##
## Fixed effects:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error    df t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)      6.9366    0.8535 53.4281   8.127 6.63e-11
## PlotTreatment      2.1535    1.0372 71.2263   2.076  0.0415
## as.factor(Year)2022  0.7519    1.0314 68.4985   0.729  0.4685
## PlotTreatment:as.factor(Year)2022 -0.7210    1.4586 68.4985  -0.494  0.6227
##
```

```
## (Intercept) ***
## PlotTreatment *
## as.factor(Year)2022
## PlotTreatment:as.factor(Year)2022
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##      (Intr) PltTrt a.(Y)2
## PlotTretmnt -0.613
## as.f(Y)2022 -0.604  0.497
## PT:.(Y)2022  0.427 -0.703 -0.707
```

```
#Means and SEs, across the two years (48 observations):
Abundance_Select_AB %>%
  group_by(Plot) %>%
  dplyr::summarize_at(vars(Count), list(Mean_Count = mean, SE_Count = se))
```

1.3 Small Flower Visitors

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 3
##   Plot      Mean_Count SE_Count
##   <chr>      <dbl>    <dbl>
## 1 Control      29.4      3.76
## 2 Treatment    47.2      8.43
```

```
# Percent Diff
Abundance_Select_AB_Percent_Diff <- Abundance_Select_AB %>%
  group_by(Plot) %>%
  dplyr::summarize_at(vars(Count), list(Mean_Count = mean, SE_Count = se))

Abundance_Select_AB_Percent_Diff %>%
  summarise(percent_diff = (100*(Mean_Count[2]-Mean_Count[1])/mean(Mean_Count)))
```

```
##   percent_diff
## 1      46.54704
```

```
# Calculate mean % difference in pollinator numbers during apple bloom, both years combined.
#Orchard ID column has to be removed.
```

```
Abundance_Select_Values_Diff <- pivot_wider(Abundance_Select_AB, id_cols=c(Site, Year), names_from = Plot)
Abundance_Select_Values_Diff$Percent_Diff <- (Abundance_Select_Values_Diff$Treatment-Abundance_Select_Values_Diff$Control)/Abundance_Select_Values_Diff$Control
```

```
#Mean percent difference in pollinator abundance:
mean(Abundance_Select_Values_Diff$Percent_Diff)
```

```
## [1] 18.58619
```

```

#Std. error of percent difference in bee abundance:
sd(Abundance_Select_Values_Diff$Percent_Diff, na.rm = T)/sqrt(length(Abundance_Select_Values_Diff$Percent_Diff))

## [1] 15.60057

```

```

# Both Years, apple bloom period only, With Year as fixed categorical variable, including interaction:
Select_Abund_GLMM_Year_All <- glmer(Count ~ Plot * as.factor(Year) + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
  family=poisson(link = "log"),
  data=Abundance_Select_AB,
  control=glmerControl(optimizer="nloptwrap"))

# Model diagnostics:
overdisp.glmer(Select_Abund_GLMM_Year_All)

```

1.3.1 Models

```
## Residual deviance: 1578.352 on 90 degrees of freedom (ratio: 17.537)
```

```
testDispersion(Select_Abund_GLMM_Year_All)
```

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 0.696

```
##
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.
```

```
## simulated
##
## data: simulationOutput
## dispersion = 0.87078, p-value = 0.696
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
simulationOutput <- simulateResiduals(fittedModel = Select_Abund_GLMM_Year_All, plot = F)
plot(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA residual


```
testZeroInflation(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA zero-inflation test via comparison to expected zeros with simulation under H0 = fitted model

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 0

```
##  
## DHARMA zero-inflation test via comparison to expected zeros with  
## simulation under H0 = fitted model  
##  
## data: simulationOutput  
## ratioObsSim = 17.241, p-value < 2.2e-16  
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
#Zero-inflated but not overdispersed.
```

```
#Zero-inflated Poisson using glmmTMB:
```

```
Select_Abund_ZI_All <- glmmTMB(Count ~ Plot * as.factor(Year) + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),  
  ziformula = ~1, family = "poisson",  
  data=Abundance_Select_AB)
```

```
# Model diagnostics:
```

```
testDispersion>Select_Abund_ZI_All)
```

DHARMa nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 0.752

```
##  
## DHARMa nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.  
## simulated  
##  
## data: simulationOutput  
## dispersion = 0.87261, p-value = 0.752  
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
simulationOutput <- simulateResiduals(fittedModel = Select_Abund_ZI_All, plot = F)  
plot(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA residual


```
testZeroInflation(simulationOutput)
```

DHARMA zero-inflation test via comparison to expected zeros with simulation under H_0 = fitted model

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p -value (two.sided) = 0.88

```
##
## DHARMA zero-inflation test via comparison to expected zeros with
## simulation under H0 = fitted model
##
## data: simulationOutput
## ratioObsSim = 1.1848, p-value = 0.88
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
#No problems.
```

```
#Selected model results:
```

```
summary(Select_Abund_ZI_All)
```

```
## Family: poisson ( log )
## Formula:      Count ~ Plot * as.factor(Year) + (1 | 'Orchard ID'/Site)
## Zero inflation:      ~1
## Data: Abundance_Select_AB
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 2079.4 2097.4 -1032.7 2065.4      89
##
## Random effects:
##
## Conditional model:
## Groups      Name      Variance Std.Dev.
## Site:'Orchard ID' (Intercept) 0.4104 0.6406
## Orchard ID      (Intercept) 0.3577 0.5981
## Number of obs: 96, groups: Site:'Orchard ID', 26; Orchard ID, 16
##
## Conditional model:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      2.755350  0.207067 13.307 < 2e-16 ***
## PlotTreatment      0.430089  0.060207  7.144 9.1e-13 ***
## as.factor(Year)2022 0.613666  0.057261 10.717 < 2e-16 ***
## PlotTreatment:as.factor(Year)2022 -0.004151  0.072312 -0.057 0.954
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Zero-inflation model:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)  -3.3901  0.5859 -5.786 7.19e-09 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

1.4 All Years

```
pdf(file="Figure 1.pdf", width=12, height=8)
```

```
#Panel A (Osmia):
```

```
Abund_Fig_Osmia <- ggplot(data=Abundance_Osmia_All, aes(x=Plot, y=Count, colour=Plot, fill=Plot)) +
```

```

scale_colour_brewer(palette = "Set1") +
scale_fill_manual(values = c(adjustcolor("#E41A1C", alpha = 0.5), adjustcolor("#377EB8", alpha = 0.5)) +
geom_boxplot(width = 0.5) +
geom_jitter(height=0, width = 0.1, size = 1) +
theme_bw() +
labs(y = expression(paste(italic("Osmia"), " observed")), x = "") +
scale_x_discrete(labels=c("control", "trapnests")) +
scale_y_continuous(trans = 'sqrt') +
facet_grid( ~ fct_relevel(Round_Year, "Apple bloom 2021", "Pre-thinning 2021", "Post-thinning 2021"))
theme(
  panel.grid.major = element_blank(),
  panel.grid.minor = element_blank(),
  axis.text=element_text(size=14),
  axis.title=element_text(size=16),
  strip.text.x = element_text(size = 16),
  legend.position="none",
  strip.background = element_rect(color="NA", fill="NA")
)
Abund_Fig_Osmia

#Panel B (all pollinators):
Abund_Fig_Bees <- ggplot(data=Abundance_Total_All, aes(x=Plot, y=Count, colour=Plot, fill=Plot)) +
  scale_colour_brewer(palette = "Set1")+
  scale_fill_manual(values = c(adjustcolor("#E41A1C", alpha = 0.5), adjustcolor("#377EB8", alpha = 0.5)) +
  geom_boxplot(width = 0.5) +
  geom_jitter(height=0, width = 0.1, size = 1) +
  theme_bw() +
  labs(y = "pollinators observed", x = "") +
  scale_x_discrete(labels=c("control", "trapnests")) +
  scale_y_continuous(trans = 'sqrt') +
  facet_grid( ~ fct_relevel(Round_Year, "Apple bloom 2021", "Pre-thinning 2021", "Post-thinning 2021"))
  theme(
    panel.grid.major = element_blank(),
    panel.grid.minor = element_blank(),
    axis.text=element_text(size=14),
    axis.title=element_text(size=16),
    legend.position="none",
    strip.background = element_rect(color="NA",fill="NA"),
    strip.text.x = element_blank()
  )
Abund_Fig_Bees

#Merge panels:
plot_grid(Abund_Fig_Osmia, Abund_Fig_Bees, nrow = 2, labels = c("a","b"), rel_heights = c(1.1,1))

```

1.4.1 Figures

2. Apple Yield and Quality

```

# Mean and SE of fruit-set pre-thinning values per plot
Apple_Values_Pre_2 <- Apple_2 %>%

```

```

group_by(Plot) %>%
dplyr::summarize(Mean_Fruit_Set_Pre=mean(Fruit_Set_Pre, na.rm = T),
                 SE_Fruit_Set_Pre=se(Fruit_Set_Pre))
Apple_Values_Pre_2

```

2.1 Pre-Thinning

```

## # A tibble: 2 x 3
##   Plot      Mean_Fruit_Set_Pre SE_Fruit_Set_Pre
##   <chr>          <dbl>          <dbl>
## 1 Control      0.187          0.0227
## 2 Treatment   0.252          0.0271

```

```

# Binomial GLMER With Site as a Random Effect

Apple_Pre_Thin_GLM <- glmer(Pre_Fruit/Buds ~ Plot + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
                           family = binomial(link = "logit"),
                           data=Apple_2)
summary(Apple_Pre_Thin_GLM)

```

2.1.1 Model

```

## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: Pre_Fruit/Buds ~ Plot + (1 | 'Orchard ID'/Site)
## Data: Apple_2
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
##    86.6    97.9   -39.3    78.6     119
##
## Scaled residuals:
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -0.3333 -0.1277  0.2893  0.7351  3.0823
##
## Random effects:
##   Groups                Name            Variance Std.Dev.
## Site:'Orchard ID' (Intercept) 0.000e+00 0.000e+00
## Orchard ID          (Intercept) 2.309e-09 4.805e-05
## Number of obs: 123, groups: Site:'Orchard ID', 23; Orchard ID, 14
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)  -2.19723    0.43033  -5.106 3.29e-07 ***
## PlotTreatment -0.05411    0.60779  -0.089  0.929
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr)

```

```
## PlotTretmnt -0.708
## optimizer (Nelder_Mead) convergence code: 0 (OK)
## boundary (singular) fit: see help('isSingular')
```

```
# Model diagnostics:
overdisp.glmer(Apple_Pre_Thin_GLM)
```

```
## Residual deviance: 45.999 on 119 degrees of freedom (ratio: 0.387)
```

```
testDispersion(Apple_Pre_Thin_GLM)
```


Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 0.024

```
##
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.
## simulated
##
## data: simulationOutput
## dispersion = 0.45244, p-value = 0.024
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
simulationOutput <- simulateResiduals(fittedModel = Apple_Pre_Thin_GLM, plot = T)
```

DHARMA residual

#Fit is terrible.

#Ordered beta regression with Site random:

```
Apple_Pre_Thin_GLM <- glmmTMB(Fruit_Set_Pre ~ Plot + (1|`Orchard ID`/Site),
                             dispformula = ~1,
                             family = ordbeta,
                             data=Apple_2)
summary(Apple_Pre_Thin_GLM)
```

```
## Family: ordbeta ( logit )
## Formula:      Fruit_Set_Pre ~ Plot + (1 | `Orchard ID`/Site)
## Data: Apple_2
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
##    -3.1    16.6     8.6   -17.1     116
##
## Random effects:
##
## Conditional model:
## Groups      Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## Site:`Orchard ID` (Intercept) 0.04552  0.2133
## Orchard ID   (Intercept) 0.17857  0.4226
## Number of obs: 123, groups: Site:`Orchard ID`, 23; Orchard ID, 14
##
## Dispersion parameter for ordbeta family (): 6.03
##
## Conditional model:
##           Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
```

```
## (Intercept)    -1.4397    0.2005   -7.179 7.03e-13 ***
## PlotTreatment    0.3110    0.1634    1.903  0.057 .
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
# Model diagnostics:
testDispersion(Apple_Pre_Thin_GLM)
```

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 1

```
##
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.
## simulated
##
## data: simulationOutput
## dispersion = 1, p-value = 1
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
simulationOutput <- simulateResiduals(fittedModel = Apple_Pre_Thin_GLM, plot = T)
```

DHARMA residual

#Much better.

2.2 All Years

```
pdf(file="Figure 2.pdf", width=8, height=8)

#Panel A (fruit set pre-thinning, 2021):
Fruit_Set_Pre_Fig_2021 <- ggplot(data=subset(Apple_All, Year == 2021), aes(x=Plot, y=Fruit_Set_Pre, col=
  scale_colour_brewer(palette = "Set1")+
  scale_fill_manual(values = c(adjustcolor("#E41A1C", alpha = 0.5), adjustcolor("#377EB8", alpha = 0.5))
  geom_boxplot(width = 0.5) +
  geom_jitter(height=0, width = 0.1, size = 1) +
  theme_bw() +
  labs(y = "fruit set (pre-thinning)", x = "") +
  ylim(0,1) +
  scale_x_discrete(labels=c("control", "trapnests")) +
  theme(
    panel.grid.major = element_blank(),
    panel.grid.minor = element_blank(),
    axis.text=element_text(size=14),
    axis.title=element_text(size=16),
    legend.position="none",
    strip.background = element_rect(color="NA",fill="NA"))
Fruit_Set_Pre_Fig_2021
```

```
# Panel B (fruit set pre-thinning, 2022):
```

```
Fruit_Set_Pre_Fig_2022 <- ggplot(data=subset(Apple_All, Year == 2022), aes(x=Plot, y=Fruit_Set_Pre, colour=Plot)) +  
  scale_colour_brewer(palette = "Set1")+  
  scale_fill_manual(values = c(adjustcolor("#E41A1C", alpha = 0.5), adjustcolor("#377EB8", alpha = 0.5))) +  
  geom_boxplot(width = 0.5) +  
  geom_jitter(height=0, width = 0.1, size = 1) +  
  theme_bw() +  
  labs(y = "fruit set (pre-thinning)", x = "") +  
  ylim(0,1) +  
  scale_x_discrete(labels=c("control", "trapnests")) +  
  theme(  
    panel.grid.major = element_blank(),  
    panel.grid.minor = element_blank(),  
    axis.text=element_text(size=14),  
    axis.title=element_text(size=16),  
    legend.position="none",  
    strip.background = element_rect(color="NA",fill="NA"))  
Fruit_Set_Pre_Fig_2022
```

```
#Panel C (fruit set post-thinning, 2021):
```

```
Fruit_Set_Post_Fig_2021 <- ggplot(data=subset(Apple_All, Year == 2021), aes(x=Plot, y=Fruit_Set_Post, colour=Plot)) +  
  scale_colour_brewer(palette = "Set1")+  
  scale_fill_manual(values = c(adjustcolor("#E41A1C", alpha = 0.5), adjustcolor("#377EB8", alpha = 0.5))) +  
  geom_boxplot(width = 0.5) +  
  geom_jitter(height=0, width = 0.1, size = 1) +  
  theme_bw() +  
  labs(y = "fruit set (post-thinning)", x = "") +  
  ylim(0,1) +  
  scale_x_discrete(labels=c("control", "trapnests")) +  
  theme(  
    panel.grid.major = element_blank(),  
    panel.grid.minor = element_blank(),  
    axis.text=element_text(size=14),  
    axis.title=element_text(size=16),  
    legend.position="none",  
    strip.background = element_rect(color="NA",fill="NA"))  
Fruit_Set_Post_Fig_2021
```

```
#Panel D (apple circumference, 2021):
```

```
Fruit_Qual_Fig_2021 <- ggplot(data=subset(Apple_All, Year == 2021), aes(x=Plot, y=Mean_Circum, colour=Plot)) +  
  scale_colour_brewer(palette = "Set1")+  
  scale_fill_manual(values = c(adjustcolor("#E41A1C", alpha = 0.5), adjustcolor("#377EB8", alpha = 0.5))) +  
  geom_boxplot(width = 0.5) +  
  geom_jitter(height=0, width = 0.1, size = 1) +  
  theme_bw() +  
  labs(y = "fruit circumference (cm)", x = "") +  
  scale_x_discrete(labels=c("control", "trapnests")) +  
  theme(  
    panel.grid.major = element_blank(),  
    panel.grid.minor = element_blank(),  
    axis.text=element_text(size=14),  
    axis.title=element_text(size=16),  
    legend.position="none",
```

```

strip.background = element_rect(color="NA",fill="NA"))
Fruit_Qual_Fig_2021

# Merge panels:
plot_grid(Fruit_Set_Pre_Fig_2021, Fruit_Set_Pre_Fig_2022, Fruit_Set_Post_Fig_2021, Fruit_Qual_Fig_2021

```

2.2.1 Figures

Supporting Information

Data Organization

1. Trap Nests

```

# Load Excel File with Data from All Rounds
Trap_Nest_Total <- read_excel("Trap_Nest_Total.xlsx", na = "N/A") %>%
  unite('Site', Orchard, 'Site ID', remove = FALSE)

# Load Excel File with Verified Trap Nest Cell Counts and Numbers (Final Round Only)
Trap_Nest_Final <- read_excel("Trap_Nest_Final_Count.xlsx", na = "N/A") %>%
  unite('Site', Orchard, 'Site ID', remove = FALSE)

# Total Number of Holes in Trap Nests
Total_Holes <- Trap_Nest_Final %>% filter(Round == "Final Count") %>%
  nrow()
Total_Holes

```

1.1 Holes Occupied

```
## [1] 2742
```

```

# Total Number of Occupied Holes in Trap Nests
Total_Occupied_Holes <- Trap_Nest_Final %>% filter(Round == "Final Count") %>%
  drop_na(`# New Cells`) %>%
  nrow()
Total_Occupied_Holes

```

```
## [1] 1582
```

```

# Percent of holes occupied (overall)
Total_Occupied_Holes/Total_Holes

```

```
## [1] 0.5769511
```

```

# Total Number of Occupied Holes in Trap Nests per Taxon per Site
Holes_Taxon_Site <- Trap_Nest_Final %>% filter(Round == "Final Count") %>%
  mutate(Taxa=replace_na(Taxa, "Unoccupied")) %>%
  group_by(Site, Taxa, .drop=FALSE) %>%
  do(data.frame(nrow=nrow(.))) %>%
  ungroup %>%
  complete(Site, nesting(Taxa)) %>%
  arrange(Taxa) %>%
  mutate(nrow = replace_na(nrow, 0))
Holes_Taxon_Site

```

```

## # A tibble: 120 x 3
##   Site Taxa      nrow
##   <chr> <chr>    <int>
## 1 CO_1 Chelostomoides    5
## 2 FO_3 Chelostomoides    2
## 3 HA_1 Chelostomoides    1
## 4 HA_2 Chelostomoides    2
## 5 HA_3 Chelostomoides    0
## 6 HC_1 Chelostomoides   10
## 7 KO_1 Chelostomoides   13
## 8 LC_1 Chelostomoides    3
## 9 MA_1 Chelostomoides    4
## 10 MA_2 Chelostomoides    1
## # i 110 more rows

```

```

# Total Number of Occupied Holes in Trap Nests per Taxon
Holes_Taxon <- Trap_Nest_Final %>% filter(Round == "Final Count") %>%
  mutate(Taxa=replace_na(Taxa, "Unoccupied")) %>%
  count("Taxa") %>%
  mutate("%" = freq/sum(freq))
Holes_Taxon

```

```

##           Taxa freq      %
## 1 Chelostomoides 104 0.03792852
## 2      Megachile 125 0.04558716
## 3       Osmia 245 0.08935084
## 4   Unoccupied 1160 0.42304887
## 5       Wasp 1108 0.40408461

```

1.2 Brood Cells Produced Calculating trap nest offspring numbers

```

# Calculating total number of brood cells across all Taxa
Trap_Nest_Final %>%
  dplyr::summarize_at(vars(`# Total Cells`), list(Total_Cells_Sum=sum)) %>%
  drop_na(Total_Cells_Sum)

# Calculating percentage of total cells produced per Taxon
Cells_Taxon_Final <- Trap_Nest_Final %>%
  group_by(Taxa) %>%
  dplyr::summarize_at(vars(`# Total Cells`), list(Total_Cells_Sum=sum)) %>%
  mutate("%" = Total_Cells_Sum/sum(Total_Cells_Sum)) %>%

```

```

    drop_na(Total_Cells_Sum)
Cells_Taxon_Final

# Calculating percentage of new cells produced during apple bloom, Round 2 (pre-apple thinning), and Round 3
Cells_Taxon_Round_Total <- Trap_Nest_Total %>%
  group_by(Taxa, Round) %>%
  dplyr::summarize_at(vars(`# New Cells`), list(New_Cells_Sum=sum)) %>%
  filter(Round != "Round 4" & Round != "Final Count") %>%
  mutate("%" = New_Cells_Sum/sum(New_Cells_Sum)) %>%
  drop_na(New_Cells_Sum)
Cells_Taxon_Round_Total

# Calculating percentage of new cells produced during apple bloom, Round 2 (pre-apple thinning), and Round 3
Cells_Taxon_Round_Site_Total <- Trap_Nest_Total %>%
  mutate(Site = as.factor(Site), Taxa = as.factor(Taxa), Round = as.factor(Round)) %>%
  group_by(Site, Taxa, Round, .drop = FALSE) %>%
  dplyr::summarize(Total_New_Cells = sum(`# New Cells`, na.rm = TRUE)) %>%
  filter(Round != "Round 4" & Round != "Final Count") %>%
  mutate("%" = Total_New_Cells/sum(Total_New_Cells)) %>%
  drop_na()
Cells_Taxon_Round_Site_Total

# Re-labeling Round 2 and Round 3
Cells_Taxon_Round_Site_Total$Round <- factor(Cells_Taxon_Round_Site_Total$Round, levels=c("Apple Bloom", "Osmia"))

# Calculating percentage of total cells produced per Site
Cells_Site_Total <- Trap_Nest_Final %>%
  group_by(Taxa, Site) %>%
  dplyr::summarize_at(vars(`# Total Cells`), list(Total_Cells=sum)) %>%
  mutate("%" = Total_Cells/sum(Total_Cells)) %>%
  drop_na()
Cells_Site_Total

```

```

#Filter for Only Osmia
Osmia_Nest <- Trap_Nest_Final %>% filter(Taxa == "Osmia") %>%
  drop_na(`# New Cells`)

#How many Osmia nests per site, how many were x-rayed at each site, and how many total brood cells, survival
#Total brood cells calculated from full dataset includes destroyed nests (total cells recorded as 0);
#x-rayed cells excludes destroyed nests.
Osmia_Nest_Summary <- Osmia_Nest %>% group_by(Site) %>%
  dplyr::summarize(Mean_Total_Cells=mean(`# Total Cells`, na.rm = T),
                  Sum_Total_Cells = sum(`# Total Cells`, na.rm = T),
                  N_Nests = n())

XRayed_Osmia_Nests <- filter(Osmia_Nest, `X-Ray Mount`!="NA")
XRay_Osmia_Survival <- XRayed_Osmia_Nests %>% group_by(Site) %>%
  dplyr::summarize(Total_XRayed_Cells=sum(`# Total Cells`, na.rm = T),
                  Total_Surv_Female_Cells=sum(`# Surviving Female Osmia`, na.rm = T),
                  Total_Surv_Osmia_Cells=sum(`# Surviving Osmia`, na.rm = T),
                  N_XRayed_Nests = n())

```

```

Osmia_Nest_Survival <- join(Osmia_Nest_Summary, XRay_Osmia_Survival)
Osmia_Nest_Survival$Lost <- Osmia_Nest_Survival$N_Nests - Osmia_Nest_Survival$N_XRayed_Nests
Osmia_Nest_Survival$Cells_Per_XRayed_Nest <-
  Osmia_Nest_Survival$Total_XRayed_Cells/Osmia_Nest_Survival$N_XRayed_Nests
Osmia_Nest_Survival$Surv_Cells_Per_XRayed_Nest <-
  Osmia_Nest_Survival$Total_Surv_Osmia_Cells/Osmia_Nest_Survival$N_XRayed_Nests
Osmia_Nest_Survival$Surv_Females_Per_XRayed_Nest <-
  Osmia_Nest_Survival$Total_Surv_Female_Cells/Osmia_Nest_Survival$N_XRayed_Nests

```

1.3 Trap-Nest Offspring Survival

```

# Load Pollen Data into a dataframe
Pollen <- read_excel("Pollen.xlsx") %>%
  as.data.frame(Pollen)

```

1.4 Pollen Usage

Results

2.1 Phenology of Trap Nest Offspring Production

```

pdf(file="Figure S5.pdf", width=10, height=6)

ggplot(Cells_Taxon_Round_Site_Total, aes(x=as.factor(Round), y = as.numeric(Total_New_Cells), fill=Taxon)) +
  geom_boxplot() +
  geom_jitter(height=0, aes(y = as.numeric(Total_New_Cells)), size = 0.5) +
  scale_fill_manual(breaks = c("Chelostomoides", "Megachile", "Osmia", "Wasp"), values=c("white", "grey", "white", "grey")) +
  scale_color_manual(breaks = c("Chelostomoides", "Megachile", "Osmia", "Wasp"), values=c("white", "grey", "white", "grey")) +
  theme_bw() +
  labs(y="Number of New Cells Produced per Site", x="") +
  theme(
    axis.ticks.x=element_blank(),
    axis.text=element_text(size=14),
    axis.title=element_text(size=16, face="bold"),
    legend.text = element_text(size=14),
    legend.title = element_text(size=16))

```

2.1.1 Figure S5

2.2 Occupancy and Brood Cell Production by Taxon

2.2.1 Holes Occupied per Taxon

```
pdf(file="Figure S3.pdf", width=8, height=6)

ggplot(Holes_Taxon_Site, aes(x=reorder(Taxa, nrow), y = nrow)) +
  geom_boxplot(fill="grey") +
  geom_jitter(height=0, size=0.25) +
  scale_x_discrete(labels = c("resin bees/wasps", "Megachile", "Osmia", "potter wasps", "unoccupied")) +
  theme_bw() +
  labs(y="Total Nest Holes per Site", x="Taxa") +
  theme(
    axis.text=element_text(size=14),
    axis.title=element_text(size=16, face="bold"))
```

2.2.1.1 Figure S3

2.2.2 Brood Cells Produced per Taxon

```
pdf(file="Figure S4.pdf", width=8, height=6)

ggplot(Cells_Site_Total, aes(x=reorder(Taxa, Total_Cells), y = Total_Cells))+
  geom_boxplot(fill="grey") +
  geom_jitter(height=0, size=0.25) +
  theme_bw() +
  labs(y="Total Cells per Site", x="Taxa") +
  theme(
    axis.text=element_text(size=14),
    axis.title=element_text(size=16, face="bold"))
```

2.2.2.1 Figure S4

2.3 Trap-Nest Offspring Survival

For Year 1 of *Osmia* spp. offspring as determined by X-ray.

```
#What percentage of all nests were completely destroyed?
Total_Lost <- sum(Osmia_Nest_Survival$Lost); Total_Nests <- sum(Osmia_Nest_Survival$N_Nests)
Total_Lost/Total_Nests
```

```
## [1] 0.2530612
```

```
#What proportion of all surviving Osmia brood cells were female?
sum(Osmia_Nest_Survival$Total_Surv_Female_Cells)/sum(Osmia_Nest_Survival$Total_Surv_Osmia_Cells)
```

```
## [1] 0.6742788
```

```
#How many total brood cells per nest on average?  
mean(Osmia_Nest_Survival$Cells_Per_Nest);
```

```
## [1] NA
```

```
sd(Osmia_Nest_Survival$Cells_Per_Nest)
```

```
## [1] NA
```

```
#Mean and SD of number of surviving females per nest:  
mean(Osmia_Nest_Survival$Surv_Females_Per_Nest);
```

```
## [1] NA
```

```
sd(Osmia_Nest_Survival$Surv_Females_Per_Nest)
```

```
## [1] NA
```

```
Pivot_Osmia_Nest_Survival <- pivot_longer(Osmia_Nest_Survival, cols = 10:12, names_to = "cell_type", va
```

```
pdf(file="Figure S6.pdf", width=8, height=6)
```

```
Figure_S6 <- ggplot(Pivot_Osmia_Nest_Survival, aes(x=factor(cell_type, level = c("Cells_Per_XRayed_Nest",  
  geom_boxplot(width = 0.5) +  
  scale_fill_brewer(palette="YlOrBr") +  
  geom_jitter(aes(cex = N_XRayed_Nests), height=0, width=0.1, pch = 21) +  
  theme_bw() +  
  labs(y="Mean Number of Offspring per Nest", x="") +  
  scale_x_discrete(labels=c("Total", "Total Surviving", "Surviving Females"))) +  
  theme(  
    legend.position = "None",  
    axis.text=element_text(size=14),  
    axis.title=element_text(size=16, face="bold"))
```

```
Figure_S6
```

2.3.1 Figure S6

2.4 Pollen Usage

```
# Summarizing pollen data by percentage  
Pollen_Values <- Pollen %>%  
  group_by(Taxa) %>%  
  dplyr::summarize_at(vars(Number_Grains), list(Number_Grains=sum)) %>%  
  mutate("%" = Number_Grains/sum(Number_Grains))
```